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PROVENANCE OF THE TABBOWA AND ANDIGAMA SEDIMENTS: HYPOTHESIZED AS BRACKISHWATER FLUVIO-DELTAIC CONDITIONS

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Undisturbed core samples from the Tabbowa (24.9 m) and Andigama (43.6 m) basins in northwestern Sri Lanka were analyzed using core logging, scanning electron microscopy, and palynomorph analysis (palynological and palynofacies). These techniques were applied to each stratigraphic layer to determine the provenance, sedimentation history, and paleoclimatic conditions. The extracted pollen suggests a paleoclimate characterized by low temperatures and humid conditions. Organic matter trapped in the sediments indicates that deposition primarily involved suspended load settling in a weakly oxygenated environment, suggesting dysoxic to anoxic conditions within a fluvio-deltaic setting. Textural features of arkosic sandstones, feldspathic sandstones, and carbonaceous sandstones reveal evidence of slow, steady, and periodic low-energy flows, which eventually led to the formation of swamps within the basin. Moreover, tidal deposits are interpreted to have formed under brackish water fluvio-deltaic conditions, with bay-head deltaic systems gradually migrating coastward. The presence of thin beds of nodular limestone indicates a rhythmic phase within the sedimentary sequence, likely formed during rapid subsidence in a brackish water environment. The sedimentological signatures strongly support the paleoenvironmental interpretations derived from palynofacies analysis. In conclusion, the sedimentation occurred under terrestrial conditions within a fluvio-deltaic environment during the Jurassic (Callovian-Kimmeridgian) and Late Jurassic to Early Cretaceous (Tithonia-Berriasian) periods.

Keywords: Tabbowa, Andigama, Fluvio-deltaic system, Jurassic, Brackish water